

The Latin American Giant Observatory

Contribution to the Latin American Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructure

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Abstract

The Latin American Giant Observatory (LAGO) is an extended cosmic ray observatory, which consists of a wide network of water Cherenkov detectors located in ten different countries. The geographic distribution of the LAGO sites, with different altitudes and geomagnetic rigidity cutoffs, combined with the new electronic system for control, atmospheric sensing and data acquisition on board of each detector, allow the realization of multiple and varied astrophysics, space physics and atmospheric physics studies at regional scale. LAGO is mainly oriented to perform basic research in three areas: high energy phenomena, space weather and atmospheric radiation at ground level. It is an observatory designed, built and operated by the LAGO Collaboration, a non-centralized collaborative union of more than 29 institutions from ten latin american countries countries plus Spain.

In this work the LAGO sites and the capabilities of the LAGO detection network, spanned across Latin America, will be described.

1. Overview

The Latin American Giant Observatory (LAGO), formerly known as the Large Aperture Gamma Ray Bursts Observatory, is a project conceived in 2006 [1] to detect the high energy component of Gamma Ray Bursts (GRBs,

with typical energy of primaries $E_p \gtrsim 20 \text{ GeV}$) by installing $10 \text{ m}^2 - 20 \text{ m}^2$ water Cherenkov detectors (WCD) at very high altitude sites across the Andean ranges. From this initial aim, LAGO has evolved toward an extended astroparticle observatory at a regional scale, currently operating WCDs and other particle detectors in ten countries in LA (Argentina, Bolivia, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Ecuador, Guatemala, Mexico, Peru and Venezuela) together with the recent incorporation of institutions from Spain. LAGO is operated by the LAGO Collaboration, a cooperative and non-centralized collaboration of 29 institutions.

Although the original plan comprised the detection of the high energy component of GRBs, recently it has been shown that WCDs can also be used to study the Solar Modulation (SM) of Galactic Cosmic Rays (GCR) and other transient phenomena, by measuring the variations of the flux of secondary particles at ground level [2]. Measuring the flux modulation of the GCR at different locations on Earth that span over a wide range of rigidity cut offs and using the same type of detectors, one can provide important information about the global structure of the magnetic cloud reaching the space environment surrounding the Earth.

Astroparticle studies in the context of GRBs [3, 4, 5], space weather and background radiation at ground level [6] are the main scientific objectives of the Latin American Giant Observatory [7].

The LAGO detection network consists of single or small arrays of astroparticle detectors installed in different sites across the Andean region [8]. Our detection network spans a region from the south of Mexico, with a small array installed at Sierra Negra (4550 m a.s.l.), to the Antarctica Peninsula, with the recent installation of two WCDs at the Marambio Base (Arg., 200 m a.s.l.), and at Macchu Picchu Base (Perú, 10 m a.s.l.), mainly oriented for Space Weather studies and monitoring [7, 9, 10].

The network is distributed over similar geographical longitudes but a wide range of geographical latitudes and altitudes. By combining simultaneous measurements at different rigidity cutoffs from regions with differing atmospheric absorption we are able to produce near-real-time information at different energy ranges of, for example, disturbances induced by interplanetary transients and long term space weather phenomena.

2. Scientific context

Astroparticle physics is nowadays one of the scientific fields that evidence large interdisciplinary contributions. This is not only possible but even needed, given the large array of topics this discipline covers: from high energy astrophysics (e.g. acceleration mechanisms) to computational sciences (e.g., data lineage and provenance). Cosmology, radiation-matter interactions, magnetohydrodynamics, Earth sciences, atmospheric science, detector physics, chemistry, biology and medical physics, have to be turned up to correctly interpret our results and to assess the extent of our predictions.

One of the important topic to address is Space Weather studies. For instance, transient solar ejecta and changes in the global structure of the heliospheric and terrestrial magnetic fields modulate the flux of low energy cosmic rays of galactic origin (GCR). Measure of the temporal variations of this flux provide information about the transport of particles in the inner and outer heliosphere.

Long-term modulations in the flux of GCR are associated with the solar cycle, while short-term are produced by interplanetary transient perturbations in the calm solar wind causing phenomena like Forbush Decreases [11]. Observed from ground level, FDs exhibit asymmetrical structures: fast decreases (several hours) of the cosmic ray flux are followed by smooth recoveries (several days). In some particular cases, they can also present more complex structures originated by intricate interplanetary Coronal Mass Ejections (iCME) phenomena such as its interactions with fast streams of plasma or with other iCMEs.

Simultaneous measurements of the GCR flux modulation at different locations on Earth using the same type of detectors, can provide important information about the global structure of the magnetic cloud reaching the near-Earth space environment. Astroparticles studies in the context of GRBs, Space Weather and background radiation at ground level are the main scientific objectives of the Latin American Giant Observatory

3. Objectives

LAGO has three main scientific objectives: to study high energy gamma events at high altitude sites, to understand space weather phenomena through monitoring the low energy cosmic rays flux at the continental scale, and to

decipher the impact (direct and indirect) of the cosmic radiation on atmospheric phenomena. These objectives are complemented by two main academic goals: to train students in astroparticle and high energy physics techniques, and foremost, to support the development of astroparticle physics in LA [12].

Scientific and academic objectives are organized in different programs and are carried out by the corresponding working groups. LAGO programs cover several aspects of the project, from the installation, calibration and operation of the detectors to the search for pathways to transfer data from remote sites.

Complete simulation chains involving all the related aspects (from CR propagation to detector response) [7, 13], see section 8, data analysis techniques specially designed for the very different energy and temporal scales of the studying phenomena [7, 14], data preservation, and the design of new experiments to be conducted in graduate and undergraduate lectures in the participating Universities, are just some examples of the range of the objectives of the LAGO project.

A feature that makes LAGO a very special experiment is that any member related to the project (being student or researcher) can access the entire performance of the experiment in one place. From the assembly of the detector, the use of electronics, calibration and various studies that can be done with this detector or data from other detectors, data analysis and simulations, students learn to conduct an astroparticle experiment in all its facets. The design of new experiments to be conducted in graduate and undergraduate lectures in the participating Universities [15], such as the muon decay observation in water or the search for Forbush decreases in the WCD data, are just some examples of the range of the academic objectives of the LAGO project. All of this shows that besides its scientific importance, the LAGO project is also a seeder for astroparticle physics development in the Andean region.

4. Methodology

The WCDs of LAGO are composed by a water container with a reflective material inside, and a photomultiplier tube (PMT) to convert the Cherenkov radiation produced by the interaction of the high energy particles with water in to an electric signal. The response of each WCD, like other particle detectors, are short electric pulses ($\sim 100\text{-}300\text{ ns}$) that are recorded by high speed (up to 240 MHz) data acquisition systems. A typical WCD of one of

Figure 1: LAGO electronics (left side): It can be seen the raspberry pi model B, the board with the Nexys2-FPGA and the custom three channels digitizer board. LAGO recipient and PMT support (right side): It can be seen the stainless steel tank to contain the water and the support to keep the PMT base above and isolated from the water of the recipient (Figure extracted from [9]).

the LAGO sites is shown in the right side of Figure 1. In this picture, the old electronic system that some of the sites are still using is shown. There is a program carried out inside the Collaboration to renew the DAQ electronics system as it is discussed below.

The PMT is connected to a electronic board that have a voltage divider, a high voltage supply, and an amplifier of the output pulse. The high voltage supply can be controlled typically from 0 V to 2000 V with a signal from 0 V to 2.5 V. The output pulse shape of the PMT depends on the geometry of the detector, for a tank of 1000 l the FWHM¹ of the pulse is around 150 ns. The data acquisition and high voltage parameters of the experiment can be settled by a PC program and the acquire pulses are transferred in real time to the PC or SBC via a USB interface. This system has the capability of acquire three or four independent channels and provide the control signal for the three or four HV supply.

Some of the key features of the data acquisition (DAQ) system of the LAGO detectors is the low budget needed to build it, the reliability and versatility. Unfortunately, the FPGA board used until now; the Nexys 2 [16] by Digilent is discontinued, making it very difficult and expensive to maintain

¹Full Width at Half Maximum

WCDs already installed and implement new detectors systems as stated in the development plan of the Collaboration [17]. Given this situation, it was necessary to decide on a plan for replacing the old electronics, trying to take advantage of the state of the art in DAQ systems now available. In this context, the new DAQ concept of all-in-one arose, and we decided on the commercial board Redpitaya STEMLab [18], as it gives us the required flexibility and low cost.

The RedPitaya STEMLab board (originally RedPitaya board) is a low-cost ($\sim 300 - 400$ USD) of-the-shelf analog signal generation/measurement electronics [18]. This commercial board is equipped with a fast dual-ADC and a fast dual-DAC, i.e., it is easy to use it as a data acquisition system and to generate output signals with an arbitrary phase difference simultaneously.

The system firmware (FW) is composed of an analog to digital converter managing block (ADC, one per channel), a baseline correction algorithm, a trigger sub-system, external sensors managing block and all the connections to the external world. All the IP blocks comply with the AXI4-Stream standard [19], which is best suited for this application. It follows the Xilinx paradigm in constructing new designs like interconnected intellectual properties blocks.

The DAQ acquires pulses from two channels simultaneously at a sampling rate of 125 MSPS. Each channel can be connected either to one PMT or to the same PMT (anode and last dynode signals) to enhance dynamic range.

In order to replicate the functionality of the Nexys2 based DAQ, a “daughterboard” has been designed and developed. This board provides different power supply voltages for the internal circuitry of the detectors; it powers the STEMLab board also. It replicates the STEMLab board interfaces to the external sensors and allows the system to be fed through a single external voltage source of 12 V. The board provides the ± 3.3 V for the signal amplifiers in the PMT’s base; the control voltage for changing the gain and the 12 V for the PMT’s high-voltage polarization. The inter-connection is done through the E1 and E2 connectors in the Redpitaya STEMLab board, where several standard communication protocols (SPI, I2C and UART) are available for plugging a variety of sensors to the system.

Using the equipment described above, all the LAGO programs exploit the single particle technique (SPT)[20] by looking for significant excesses in the counting of background signals at different sites. While this technique has the lack of directional reconstruction, it is however possible to use atmospheric absorption as a selection tool for periodic signals including gamma point

sources. Data stacking or summation in two different time systems, solar and sidereal, were made over the data. The idea behind this process is based on the random, Poissonian nature of the majority of the radiation measured by our detectors. When a non random and periodic signal exists, data can be summed over repetitive occurrences, both in sidereal and solar time, to increase the signal-to-noise ratio. After doing this, we observed clear indications, both in phase and in amplitude, of solar modulation of the flux of galactic cosmic rays. These observations demonstrate that, by using an adapted analysis technique to the characteristics of our small detectors, it is possible to observe space weather phenomena at different time scales from ground level in the LAGO network of WCD.

High altitude sites ($h > 4500$ m) are designed and operated mainly for the search of high energy components of GRB. Such sites are chosen to diminish the atmospheric absorption of extensive air showers (EAS) initiated by low energy cosmic rays. To increase electromagnetic-muon separation at single pulse level in high-altitude sites, a method based on the total charge and pulse rise-time analysis is also implemented. The increase in separation performance can be used to improve the search for possible GRB candidates, as gamma initiated showers show lower muon fractions at detector level when compared with hadronic primaries.

Simultaneous measurements of galactic cosmic ray flux modulation at different locations on Earth using the same type of detector can provide important information on the properties and global structure of magnetic clouds reaching the terrestrial environment during interplanetary Coronal Mass Ejections (ICME) events pointing towards Earth [21]. By using WCDs, we are able to determine the flux of secondary particles at different bands of deposited energy within the detector volume. These bands are dominated by different components of the CR spectrum reaching the Earth's atmosphere (primaries). This multi-spectral analysis technique (MSAT) constitutes the basis of our Space Weather oriented data analysis [7]. By combining all the data measured at different locations of the detection network, the LAGO project will provide very detailed and simultaneous information of the temporal evolution and small- and large-scale characteristics of the disturbances produced by different transient and long-term space weather phenomena.

A complex and complete chain of simulations support this program [6, 7, 13]. For every LAGO site, the directional rigidity cutoff R_c is determined for secular and disturbed geomagnetic field conditions, such as those produced during intense geomagnetic storms. The expected number of primaries is

then determined by integrating the measured flux of all the hadronic cosmic rays with $1 < E_p/\text{GeV} < 10^6$. A set of CORSIKA simulations is then used to determine the expected number of secondary particles at ground level. Only those secondaries originating from primaries with rigidities above local cut-offs are included. Finally, the expected secondary particles are injected into a Geant4-based model of the LAGO WCD to obtain the signal light flux at the detector level. All this is described in detail in section 8.

With the LAGO MSAT we are able to determine the evolution of the flux observed in three different bands. As the transition points between these different regimes are characterized by changes in the histogram slopes, a fully automated algorithm searches for all these features in 1-hour calibration histograms. As an example, in the right panel of Figure 2 the measurement of the Forbush decrease occurred on March 8th, 2012, is shown for the electromagnetic dominated band. These measurements demonstrate the capabilities of WCDs to extend present studies of space weather phenomena using low cost detectors from ground level.

Academic objectives, implemented through the LAGO Universities program, are carried out by a series of experiments and data analysis tools designed to take advantage of having a complete LAGO detector at each participating university[15, 22]. In particular, using a single WCD it is possible to measure the lifetime of atmospheric muons in water. These particles are constantly produced mainly through the decay of charged pions at typical altitudes of a few kilometers above Earth surface. By looking at the time distribution of the signals in the WCD, undergraduate or graduate students are able to determine the lifetime of low energy muons decaying inside the WCD. This simple experiment can be used in undergraduate experimental physics courses to introduce multiple complex concepts such as: Lorentz time dilation, weak interaction processes, radiation detectors physics, statistics, atmospheric physics and data analysis techniques[23].

5. List of interested scientists in the community

Please see <http://lagoproject.net/collab.html>

6. Current status and expected challenges

LAGO is an extended observatory of water Cherenkov detectors (WCDs) at continental scale. Current detectors cover a large range of geomagnetic rigidity cutoffs and atmospheric absorption depths [8], (see Figure3).

Figure 2: Left: Signal alert for a potential event candidate registered on Wed Dec 07 15:47:02.378 UTC 2011 detected by LAGO at Chacaltaya, Bolivia, 5250 m a.s.l. (from [3]). Right: Multi-spectral analysis of the Forbush Decrease of March 8th, 2012, measured in a single 1.8m² WCD in Bariloche, Argentina (red stars), compared with neutron flux measured by the Rome neutron monitor (gray pluses).

A compilation of the locations, number of detectors, altitudes, rigidity cut off, latitude and longitude, is made in table 1. It is worth mention some highlights of this table related to the LAGO science capabilities.

7. Timeline, construction and operational costs

The relatively inexpensive WCD and the off-the-shelf electronics make it affordable for most of LA institutions to participate in this unique collaboration, which incorporate not only astroparticle instrumentation but also High-Performance Computing simulations and data handling, preservation and dissemination. A collaborative network, as LAGO, that shares knowledge and technologies across Latin America has a profound impact on the development of young scientists and local communities, by sharing the last developments in ultra-fast electronics, High-Performance Computing methods and techniques; design and setting-up of novel radiation detectors with potential applications to other areas such as, e.g., medical physics. This collaborative spirit, that characterizes the way of working of big HEP experiments and AP observatories, is the central conviction of the LAGO Collaboration, which is complemented by a profound commitment to the training of young scientists. With central cases of study like the muon decay or the association of projects like Escaramujo, LAGO has contributed largely to the training of students in a lot of Latin America countries in the astroparticle

Figure 3: (left) Geographical distribution and altitudes of the Latin American Giant Observatory water Cherenkov detectors: the ones in operation are represented with blue triangles, orange squares are used for those in deployment and the planned sites are indicated in red circles. (right) Vertical rigidity cutoff at each Latin American Giant Observatory site.

physics field. Also, the development of a simple DAQ system for the LAGO detectors has opened a wide range of contributions towards the collaboration. LAGO has different levels of developments at each node of the detection network. The need for a stable and uniform operation of the current sites and the development of new sites, especially in the Antarctica region, at high altitude mountains, and in Central America, is crucial at this point in the development of the entire scientific program, so we are foreseeing the need for a common funding support for all the Observatory. The projections can be separated into two groups, one related to detectors uniformization goals and the other to the academic objectives.

For the first we propose the following milestones:

- new electronic design and characterization, Dec 2019
- new electronic deployment at all the sites, June 2020

Country	Site	Altitude [m a.s.l.]	Rigidity cut off [GV]	Latitude [deg]	Longitude [deg]
Argentina	Bariloche	850	7.8	41.15 S	71.30 W
	Buenos Aires	10	8.2	34.54 S	58.44 W
	Marambio	200	2.2	64.24 S	56.62 W
	Tucumán	430	9.4	65.11 S	26.50 W
Bolivia	Chacaltaya	5240	11.6	16.35 S	68.13 W
	Cota Cota	3917	11.6	16.41 S	68.5 W
	La Paz	3630	11.6	16.41 S	68.5 W
Brazil	Campinas	685	9.7	22.9 S	47.06 W
	Campina Grande	550	11.9	-7.23 S	35.88 W
	Sao Paulo	760	9.7	23.38 S	46.31 W
Chile	La Serena	28	9.3	29.90 S	71.25 W
	Viña del Mar	347	9.2	33.07 S	71.55 W
Colombia	Bucaramanga	956	11.6	7.14 N	73.12 W
	Pasto	2530	12.2	1.21 S	77.28 W
Ecuador	Riobamba	2750	12.3	1.81 S	78.74 W
	Quito-USFQ	2200	12.2	0.2 S	78.5 W
	Quito-EPN	2850	12.2	0.2 S	78.5 W
Guatemala	Guatemala	1490	9.1	14.63 N	90.59 W
	Tacana	4060	9.1	15.13 N	92.11 W
México	Chiapas	522	9.1	16.75 N	93.12 W
	Sierra Negra	4550	7.4	18.16 N	97.95 W
Perú	Lima	150	12.0	12.10 S	77.02 W
	Cusco	3400	11.9	13.52 S	71.96 W
	Huancayo	3370	12.0	12.04 S	75.30 W
	Macchu Picchu	10	2.2	62.09 S	58.46 W
Venezuela	Caracas-UCV	900	12.0	10.49 N	66.89 W
	Caracas-USB	900	11.7	10.49 N	66.89 W
	Mérida-ULA	1893	11.6	8.63 N	71.15 W
	Pico Espejo-ULA	4700	11.6	8.32 N	71.03 W

Table 1: Table of the different locations of the LAGO sites. Please note that the sites of Marambio and Macchu Picchu are installed at Argentinian and Peruvian antarctic bases.

- Search and identification of new potential sites, 2020

- Central LAGO Data Repository and data analysis chain, 2020-2021
- Selection and deployment of new detectors in the region, 2021
- Replacement and deployment of permanent detectors in Antarctica, 2019-2021C

The academic objectives can be sustained by the organization of two schools per year at different LAGO sites, mainly at those new places with the following schema:

- 2019: two schools (South America and North America)
- 2020: two schools (South America and Central America)
- 2021: two schools (Central America and South America)
- 2022: two schools (South America)
- 2023: two schools (South America and Central America)

The core cost of all this development is estimated at the level of 1M\$ for the following 5 years.

Given the unique way in which it was developed, the decentralized operation of the LAGO Collaboration has the consequence of being mostly funded by local University projects. The need for a global funding to provide electronic components to uniformize the operation of the detection network is mandatory. Nowadays WCD of each site has their own shape (usually a commercial cylindrical water tank bought locally) and most of the 8" to 9" PMTs were donated by the Pierre Auger Observatory. But those PMTs are starting to fail and finding replacement is expensive. At this moment, we are building a DAQ system using commercial devices like the StemLab 125-14 (formerly known as RedPitaya), but the slow control has to be implemented as a supplementary board. On the other hand, the need to train students and transfer developments across Latin America can be satisfied by organizing two international schools at different places each year with the participation of 30 to 50 LA students and 5 to 10 local and regional experts. One of those schools should be synchronized with the annual meeting of the LAGO Collaboration. While it is not an expensive development, the situation of most Latin American countries has led to difficulties to get funding, including for travel expenditures for students and even for the senior researchers.

8. Computing requirements

Here, we describe the specific software that the Collaboration have developed during the years for DAQ, called 'AQUA' and the different levels of analyses specified for the science case, called 'ANNA'. It is also included a simulation framework developed to assess the cosmic background radiation at each site, called 'ARTI'.

8.1. ACQUA

ACQUA is the acquisition system for LAGO's WCD covering from digitalization of the signal to raw data transfer to the LAGO repository. ACQUA adapts to each version of the WCD electronics, via C++, bash and perl codes, allowed setting the basic configuration of each detector, e.g. thresholds, file names and meta data as WCD dimensions, PMT reference, etc.

8.2. ANNA

ANNA is the framework codes, based on C++, for data analysis of the LAGO Observatory. ANNA performs the analysis in several levels, starting in level zero (l0), then level one (l1), etc, where each level is based on the previous one. For instance, l0 is focused on first data clean (electronic noise mainly) and getting the calibration files, used them for l1 analysis.

8.3. The Simulation Framework ARTI

Each LAGO's WCD is designed and modeled to estimate its responses to cosmic background radiation according to its geographical position. To this end, the LAGO Collaboration has developed ARTI, a framework of codes focused on estimating the cosmic ground radiation flux and the WCD's response to it, articulating CORSIKA² program [24] and Geant4³ toolkit [25].

The Cosmic ground radiation is calculated for each LAGO site following the method developed by the Collaboration [6]. This method consist of three steps. First one is about to calculating GCR flux (Φ) at an altitude of 112 km a.s.l., in accordance to the Linsley atmospheric model [26], which states that

²<https://www.ikp.kit.edu/corsika/>

³<http://geant4.web.cern.ch/>

the mass overburden is vanished [24]. For this step, geomagnetic field correction is including using IGRF and Tsynganekov 2001 models [6, for more details]. Here, Φ is considered as:

$$\Phi(E_p, Z, A, \Omega) \simeq j_0(Z, A) \left(\frac{E_p}{E_0} \right)^{\alpha(E_p, Z, A)}, \quad (1)$$

where E_p is the energy of the particle, $\alpha(E_p, Z, A)$ is considered constant with respect to the energy, i.e., $\alpha(E_p, Z, A) \approx \alpha(Z, A)$, from 10^{11} eV to 10^{15} eV [27] and E_0 has a value of 10^{12} eV [6].

So Φ is used as input by ARTI in the second step, i.e, the CORSIKA code [24]. CORSIKA calculates secondary particles produced by the interaction of each GCR with the atmosphere, then we can estimate the expected flux of secondary particles at the detector level, therefore for each LAGO site. Because in this step the atmospheric profile is a key factor for the production of secondary particles, we have set atmospheric MODTRAN profiles models [28] according to respective geographic position.

The third step of ARTI framework is the WCD's response to secondaries particles. For this, the Collaboration has implemented a computational model based on Geant4 code. This model allows a detailed simulation of the interaction between secondary particles with the WCD and then to estimates the signal registered by the detector. Because no all LAGO WCD share the same geometrical dimensions, but always conserve the cylindrical one, this model enables to fit radio and heigh, as well as the Photo-multiplier-tube and its location on the detector -at center and top of the cylinder- [1]. For more detail of this model see [13].

8.4. Data reproducibility and curation

LAGO structures their data in a four-layer scheme: raw (simply measured data); preliminary (preprocessed data with low resolution and the atmospheric pressure correction); quality (scalers corrected by both the atmospheric variables and the detector efficiency coordinate); and, high quality (corrected and fully operational histograms). For the sake of completion, LAGO roughly measures 2 TB/month, the half of which is pre-processed and lately stored for research purposes. Simulation data is around 2 TB/month too.

The first step towards convergence in federating data and services is interfacing the infrastructure resources themselves. In LAGO (and as a consequence, in EOSC afterwards), those resources will be provided by the Collaboration sites both in terms of WCDs and IT infrastructure.

In LAGO, resilience -understood as "the persistence of service delivery that can justifiably be trusted, when facing changes" [29], is provided through the careful election of robust providers and the reactivity against performance issues. In this sense, LAGO adapts the paradigm developed by the European Open Science Cloud, i.e. EOSC-hub [30].

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